

RPC as a Functor: Cross-Platform Type Sharing

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Abstract

The categories of data types are used in this paper to study programming languages in cross-platform distributed systems. We introduce the concept of functor to better understand the remote procedure call (RPC). When many programming languages are involved, type sharing plays an essential role in enabling the RPC as a functor. We also discussed a method to automatically implement the type sharing in the coding level.

1 Introduction

This paper proposes a systematic approach to designing cross-platform distributed systems. The concept **cross-platform** stands for applications(programs) developed in different programming languages. In this case, one of the most fundamental challenges is the inter-operation of different data **type systems** supported by different programming languages.

For decades, **Remote Procedure Call (RPC)** has been a standard approach for the implementation of distributed systems. Typically a client calls remote functions (procedures) on a server and expects a result like running on the local host. Today Rest API is more popular, while the idea is similar. What we discuss in this paper also applies to the Rest API approach. The **procedure** in RPC is the concept we will study thoroughly. We use the mathematically strict term (pure) **function** instead.

RPC plays an important role in distributed systems. However, the design of a RPC system is not easy, since it is intrinsically cross-platform. Usually in this situation, a protocol is required. When designing a protocol, one used to weaken the concept of type to accommodate heterogeneous environments. However, we advocate strong-**typed protocol** and let type itself play a central role in the design of a protocol.

The main contributions of this paper include:

- Introduce the concept of functor to understand the RPC approach
- Provide a category for type sharing among different programming languages
- Propose a method to automatically implement the type sharing in the coding level
- Hence let the RPC as a functor works without the heavy burden of human coding

This paper discusses type systems intensively using **category theory**. For basic concepts of category theory, a few references are provided. [5] is the standard textbook for mathematicians but programmers. [7] is a modern textbook. For computer scientists interested in category theory, [4] is recommended. [3] and [1] are also good introductory guides.

We advocate strong-typed functional programming languages that have been equipped with much better type induction and error-correction capabilities. [2] gives the conceptual relationship between category theory and functional programming.

[9] and [8] presents a good example of data migration between relational data schema, using the principles of category theory. Data migration is essentially about type conversion. In this paper, we focus on type systems in general.

2 Category

Before diving into system architecture practice, let's introduce some basic concepts of category theory.

Arrow Being the most abstract branch of mathematics, category theory fundamentally studies arrows. Arrow is more officially called **morphism** by mathematicians. There are omnipresent structure-preserving maps from one mathematical structure to another of the same type, like homomorphisms between groups, homeomorphisms between topological spaces, linear maps between linear spaces, etc. These structure-preserving maps can be displayed in arrows.

An **arrow (morphism)** f has a direction. The source end is called the **Domain**, denoted $\text{Dom } f$. The target end is called the **Codomain**, denoted $\text{Cod } f$. In category theory, almost everything has a dual by reversing the direction of arrows. It explains the naming of the pair domain/codomain. "Co" is a prefix about duality, just like sine/cosine, tangent/cotangent, vector/covector, etc.

In this paper, we talk about functions in programming languages. The following function that calculates exponentials can be deemed as an arrow:

```
// f: int -> float
let f(x) = e^x
```

To understand why function f is an arrow, notice that:

$$\text{Dom } f = \text{int}, \text{Cod } f = \text{float}$$

This is nothing but the **signature** or **type annotation**(the function itself is a type) of a function in the literature of programming. A function is an arrow from one type to the other.

```
// f: int -> float
let f(x) = e^x

// g: float -> string
let g(y) = "The value is " + y.ToString()
```

Notice that the functions $f: \text{int} \rightarrow \text{float}$ and $g: \text{float} \rightarrow \text{string}$ are **composable**:

```
// (g >> f): int -> string
g(f(x)) = (g >> f)(x)
```

They have a composition because the type *float* is an intermediate type. Using the notation of category theory: let $f: X \rightarrow Y$ and $g: Y \rightarrow Z$ be arrows. Since $\text{Cod } f = Y = \text{Dom } g$, they can be composited into a new arrow $g \circ f: X \rightarrow Z$.

Category All those concepts of arrow, domain, codomain and composition of arrows should be studied in a "container" called category:

Definition .1. A **category** \mathcal{C} contains:

1. A collection¹ of **objects**,² denoted $\text{Ob}(\mathcal{C})$. If an object X belongs to the collection, we denote $X \in \text{Ob}(\mathcal{C})$ or $X \in \mathcal{C}$.
2. A collection of **arrows(morphisms)** denoted $\text{Mor}(\mathcal{C})$. If an arrow b belongs to the collection, we denote $f \in \text{Mor}(\mathcal{C})$ or $f \in \mathcal{C}$. Both the ends of such an arrow $\forall f \in \text{Mor}(\mathcal{C})$ are objects of the category, i.e. $\text{Dom } f, \text{Cod } f \in \mathcal{C}$.

Given objects $X, Y \in \mathcal{C}$, the collection of arrows $X \rightarrow Y$ is the **hom-set** from X to Y , denoted $\mathcal{C}(X, Y)$. $f: X \rightarrow Y$ is equivalent to $f \in \mathcal{C}(X, Y)$. An arrow (morphism) from $X \in \mathcal{C}$ to itself, i.e. $f: X \rightarrow X$ is called an **endomorphism**. The collections of endomorphisms on X is denoted $\text{End } X = \mathcal{C}(X, X)$. Category \mathcal{C} satisfies the following axioms:

1. $\forall X, Y, Z \in \mathcal{C}$, composition always available s.t. $\mathcal{C}(X, Y) \times \mathcal{C}(Y, Z) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}(X, Z) :: (f, g) \mapsto g \circ f$
2. The composition is associative
3. $\forall X \in \mathcal{C}, \exists ! 1_X \in \text{End } X$ as the unique **identity**.

¹We deliberately use "collection" instead of "set" frequently because in some situations the collection cannot be a set.

²Throughout this paper, the word **object** refers to this mathematical definition. Please do not confuse it with the usual concept of objects in the context of Object-Oriented Programming (OOP).

3 Category of data types

Programming language The immediate example of a category is programming. A programming language L (preferably a strong typed programming language)³ forms a **category** \mathcal{L} . The slogan *Programming language = Data structure + Algorithm* is understood by revisiting the definition of category above: a **category** \mathcal{L} contains:

1. A collection of **types** as objects. A type $X \in \mathcal{L}$ means the language L supports type X . The following are common types:

```
type X = int
type Y = float
type Z = string
```

2. A collection of **functions** as arrows. denoted $\text{Mor}(\mathcal{L})$. If a function f belongs to the collection, we denote $f \in \mathcal{L}$. The input type $\text{Dom } f$ and the output type Cod are objects in \mathcal{L} .

```
f: X -> Y
g: Y -> Z
```

Given types $X, Y \in \mathcal{C}$, the collection of functions $X \rightarrow Y$ is the hom-set $\mathcal{L}(X, Y)$. $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is equivalent to $f \in \mathcal{L}(X, Y)$. The first one is precisely the **type annotation** or **signature** of a function in many programming languages. Category \mathcal{L} satisfies the following axioms:

1. $\forall X, Y, Z \in \mathcal{C}$, the composition of $f : X \rightarrow Y$ and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ exists s.t. $g \circ f : X \rightarrow Z$

```
f: X -> Y
g: Y -> Z

(g >> f): X -> Z
```

2. The composition is associative

```
f: X -> Y
g: Y -> Z
h: Z -> A

(g >> f): X -> Z
(h >> g): Y -> A
(h >> (g >> f)): X -> A
((h >> g) >> f): X -> A

h >> (g >> f) = (h >> g) >> f
```

3. Given a type $\forall X \in \mathcal{L}$, $\exists! 1_X \in \text{End } X$ as the unique identity.

³In a strong typed programming language, the compiler strictly checks the types of the inputs and outputs of the functions to prevent mistyped error.

```
// id: X -> Z
let id x = x
```

s.t. the **objects** are the types of L and the **morphisms** are the pure functions. Functions have the highest priority in **functional programming** (FP). Mathematically a function is given in the following form:

$$f : X \rightarrow Y \text{ or } f \in \mathcal{L}(X, Y)$$

where $f : X \rightarrow Y$ has the same **type annotation** like in the above codes as in most FPs, while $f \in \mathcal{L}(X, Y)$ explicitly provides a form of an element f in the set $\mathcal{L}(X, Y)$. Such a set of morphisms (functions here in category \mathcal{L}) from one object to another (from one type to another here) is called the **hom-set**(homomorphism set). Let L be a programming language. Here is an example of a function with the input type of integer and the output type of float:

```
let f(x:int):float = e^x
```

Also notice that $(int \rightarrow float)$ is a type thus f is a $(int \rightarrow float)$ -annotated value, thus:

```
f:int -> float
```

Equivalent functions A mathematical function can have different programming implementations, for example:

```
let f1 (x) =
  x + 1

let f2 (x) =
  (x + 2) - 1
```

From an external perspective, we cannot distinguish these functions by observing input/output pairs. They are **equivalent** functions. Often we make small alterations to the definition of the arrows in the category to introduce the **modulo** of the equivalence relation:

$$f \sim g : \iff \forall x : X, f(x) = g(x)$$

4 RPC as a functor

A function is an arrow from one type to another type. One of the main objectives of RPC is to let the local caller feel like calling a local function. RPC involves two functions, the "real" remote procedure function and the "virtual" local function. Coming up with the mathematical tool we need to create their correspondence.

Functor Category theory is empowered by the concept of functor that enormously extended the concept of function(mapping). Generally speaking, a function maps a source point to a target point, while a functor is of higher order that it maps a source function to a target function.

Definition .2. A functor $F : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$ is a correspondence of objects and arrows from a category \mathcal{C} to another category \mathcal{D} s.t. the following square diagram **commutes**:

Here is a standard **commutative diagram**. A diagram commutes if the choice of arrow composition path has no difference when the ends are fixed. The above diagram commutes, i.e., $f' \circ F = F \circ f$. The functor F sends an arrow $f \in \mathcal{C}$ to $f' \in \mathcal{D}$, meanwhile, the objects $X, Y \in \mathcal{C}$ of the ends of f are simultaneously sent to the objects $X', Y' \in \mathcal{D}$ as the ends of f' . An example is helpful:

Here $F = Array.map$ is the functor that sends a $(int \rightarrow float)$ -type function into a $(int[] \rightarrow float[])$ -type function:

```

// F send a type to the array of the type
// F: 'T -> 'T[]
// 'T is a generic type
F item = [| item |]
x':int[] = F x = [| x |]
y':float[] = F y = [| y |]

// F send a function to another function
F f = Array.map f

// f: int -> float
f(x:int) = e^x

// f': int[] -> float[]
f' = F f = Array.map f

// For example:

let x:int = 2
let y:float = f x

// Commutes: (f' >> F) = (F >> f)
(f' >> F) x = f' (F x) = f' [| x |] = (Array.map f) [| x |] = [| f x |]
(F >> f) x = F (f x) = [| f x |]

```

RPC In a cross-platform distributed system, the real remote function and the virtual local function are written in different languages. Let the remote function be in language LL and the local function be in LL . Using the concepts mentioned above, there are two categories \mathcal{L}_1 and \mathcal{L}_2 , respectively. Ideally, we work on the implementation of the real remote function and expose it to be called remotely. We hope the rest of the work of exposing the function can be accomplished easily, which is the goal of this paper. Let $f \in \mathcal{L}_1$ be such a real remote function and let $f' \in \mathcal{L}_2$ be the virtual local function. What we need is exactly a functor:

$$\mathcal{L}_1 \xrightarrow{F} \mathcal{L}_2$$

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
X & \xrightarrow{F} & X' \\
\downarrow f & \xRightarrow{F} & \downarrow f' \\
Y & \xrightarrow{F} & Y'
\end{array}$$

For example, a TypeScript code running in a browser has to call an exponential function $f(x) = e^x$ in F# code running in the server. The type annotation is $f : int \rightarrow float$ in F#. TypeScript only supports

number type so what we can expect is $f' : \text{number} \rightarrow \text{number}$ in TypeScript. Then the functor works in the following way:

The functor F sends types and functions from one category to another. On one hand, it sends the real remote function to the virtual local function. On the other hand, it works as a type mapper. According to the definition of a functor, we expect $f' \circ F = F \circ f$. In plain words:

- $F \circ f$: Call the real function f in the server to get a *float*-type result. Send it to the browser and it is converted into a **number**-type result.
- $f' \circ F$: Map the *int*-type input in server into the *number*-type input in the browser. The browser feels like calling a virtual function f' .

Through functor F we automatically obtained the virtual local function f' by just calling the real remote function f . The only thing left, which is the most troublesome part, is how F works as a type mapper. This is worthy of a thorough discussion in the remainder of this paper.

5 Type sharing

Serialization/Deserialization (S/D) Let $W \in \mathcal{L}$ be a fixed type. If $\forall T \in \mathcal{L}$ another type $\exists s, d \in \mathcal{L}$ s.t. s and d are mutual inverse:⁴

Then the data of any type T can be preserved in type W , and vice versa. The most fundamental example of type W is the type of binary bits like *byte[]*. In memory image (exactly the compiler maps all the type into) and underlying network communications, *byte[]* is substantial. The type of character string like *string* is also well-known because this type is human-readable. Many of the basic data types are based on *string* like *XML* and *JSON*. Because of their recursive structure, both *XML* and *JSON* satisfied the requirement of the type W .

We will discuss type W instead of concrete types like *byte[]* or *string* to avoid the details in the programming languages. The deterministic mapping in the direction of $s : T \rightarrow W$ (resp. $d : W \rightarrow T$) is called **serialization** (resp. **deserialization**), if s and d are mutually inverse. Let **S/D** be the abbreviation

⁴To be more precise, the condition of the mutual inverse is not easy to meet. When convert a data of some type into binary bytes or JSON string, redundancy is unavoidable. In the contrary, when parse binary bytes or JSON string, data validation is necessary.

of serialization/deserialization. With S/D, the information of an element $t:T$ is preserved and various kinds of data communication are made possible, where the concept of protocol emerges.

Higher order function Notice that a function as an arrow sends the domain type to the codomain type. The function itself has its own type. The following type annotation is an example:

```
f:int -> float
```

Let T be the function type $int \rightarrow float$, i.e. the signature. Is $f : T$ serializable/deserializable in-to/out-of W ? This is what a compiler does. The compiler c is a function that maps an element $f : T$ of the function type into an element of type W . Formally:

$$c : T \rightarrow W$$

$$f \mapsto c(f)$$

W can be bytes. A compiler yields byte codes(virtual machine) or machine codes(instruction set of a processor) in this form. Byte code is the shared code for multiple programming languages running on the .NET framework. A programming language calls the functions compiled as serialized byte code.

Relational database In the relational model, data is organized in **tables**. Each table has a few **columns** with types (usually primitive types like *integer*, *string*, *bool*, etc.). The **rows** of the table are data entries. In our context, a table could be regarded as a composite type of the columns.

In many cases, a **Relational Database Management System(RDBMS)** runs as a back-end service and allows multiple clients to access it. Each of the clients could be an independent cross-platform program running remotely. Tables in the relational databases are shared types in this situation.

Cross-platform Intra-platform refers to the development in the same programming language L . In this scenario, a type $T \in \mathcal{L}$ in the category can be shared by different programs written by the same language L . The communication can be based on the serialization/deserialization of the data of type T in-to/out-of W .

In real world cross-platform (developing in different programming languages) distributed context, the design of a protocol traditionally is usually not so "typed". Since a protocol can become a technical specification linking various hosts across a network, one does not expect coupling the the protocol to specific programming languages. "Transparency" becomes a key design objective. However, What we advocate here is the **typed protocol**: S/D does not "detype" the data but preserves the structure of the types of the data.

Category of all programming languages Put all the types of all the programming languages together, we have a category $\hat{\mathcal{L}}$ to accommodate all these types. Many programming languages have the integer type. Many languages distinguish *int64* (64-bit signed integer), *int32* (32-bit signed integer), *uint32* (32-bit unsigned integer), etc. In TypeScript every kind of number has the same type *number*. Type *int32* is

supported in F# and type *number* is supported in TypeScript, but not vice versa.

In the category $\hat{\mathcal{L}}$ of all programming languages, a direct function from type *int32* of F# to *number* of TypeScript is impossible. This phenomenon perfectly demonstrates that there is no such a function that accept a type of data of one language and yield an other type of data of another language. It is cross-platform.

The solution is simple: since both F# and TypeScript support type *string*, let the commonly shared type $W = \text{string}$. Via S/D the data can be communicated crossing-form from one language to another. Let s_1 is the serialization function from *int32* to $W = \text{string}$. Let d_2 be the deserialization function from $W = \text{string}$ to *number*:

There is a **path** $\text{int32} \rightarrow \text{string} \rightarrow \text{Number}$. According to the definition of the category, every morphism (here is the pure function in $\hat{\mathcal{L}}$) in a category should be composable. The composition $d_2 \circ s_1$ has a type annotation of $(\text{int32} \rightarrow \text{number})$.

```
s1: int32 -> string // F# code
d_2:string -> number // JavaScript code
(d_2 >> s_1): int32 -> number // Cross-platform composition of f and g
```

Since almost every programming language supports type *string*, it explains why string-based JSON is so popular. But obviously, binary array type *byte[]* is more efficient. To avoid argument on binary or string type, we use type W denoting any types that could used for S/D.

Topology The path from type to type is a subject of topology, or more abstractly the category theory. The precise definition of a **topological space** is abstract and deviates from our focus. Intuitively topology studies **continuous** maps. ⁵ Given a topological space X :

- The points $\forall x, y, z, \dots \in X$ in the space are defined as the objects
- The directional path $f : x \rightarrow y, g : y \rightarrow z, \dots$ embedded in the space are defined as the arrows

It is not difficult to prove that X forms a category. The connectivity between any pair of points $x, y \in X$ depends on if there is a path linking them. The composition of paths yield new paths.

As for the category of all programming languages $\hat{\mathcal{L}}$, if there exists a (possibly composited) path from type A to type B , then the data can be mapped. The intermediate type *string* is shared by more than one

⁵Category theory has quite a few ideas from topology. The arrows as they look like are essentially "continuous" in many cases.

programming language, making cross-platform connection possible. Those types can be "accessed" by more than one programming language is called **shared types**.

RPC Previously we discussed RPC as a functor F from the category \mathcal{L}_1 of one language L_1 to another category \mathcal{L}_2 of another language L_2 , denoted $F : \mathcal{L}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{L}_2$. Now We have a category $\hat{\mathcal{L}}$ of all programming languages. The functor F becomes an **endofunctor**, i.e., a functor from one category to itself, denoted $F : \hat{\mathcal{L}} \rightarrow \hat{\mathcal{L}}$.

6 Automated coding

Previously we outlined a method to enable RPC by functor and type sharing. This approach is deterministic and the result is predictable. The only thing left is coding, especially coding for S/D of all the shared types, i.e., the types that appear in the protocol.

The design and organization of data types are crucial to the design of the entire system. Real-world development may involve many types, including types reflected from the relational database and memory-only runtime data types. However, coding for D/S functions is boring. Man-made coding cannot avoid bugs and the testing job is heavy.

In most programming languages, D/S of primitive data types like *int64*, *boolean*, *string* in-to/out-of *byte[]* or *JSON* are available. They are the building blocks for D/S of complicated custom types. In this section, we introduce practical methods to make S/D coding easy. We focus on compound types and generic types. They cover most of the custom types.

Compound types Like a **binary function** that takes a pair of parameters in the form of $f : X \times Y \rightarrow Z$, an **bifunctor** takes a pair of objects as input in the form of $F : \mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{E}$. Suppose we have a category \mathcal{L} of a given programming language L . Let $\forall X, Y \in \mathcal{L}$ be types of L . Our scope of discussion is limited to the category \mathcal{L} of programming language L_1 or the category $\hat{\mathcal{L}}$ of all programming languages, which are **Cartesian Closed Categories (CCC)**[3] that allows a dual pair of type operations. We consider the bifunctor in the form of $F : \mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$, the dual operations are well-known:

- **Product** of types as a bifunctor: $X \times Y \rightarrow X \times Y$, the categorical product or the cartesian product
- **Sum** of types as a bifunctor: $X \times Y \rightarrow X + Y$, the categorical coproduct or the disjoint union

Suppose $W \in \mathcal{L}$ is a type serving for D/S. There are $(s_X : X \rightarrow W, d_X : W \rightarrow X)$ and $(s_Y : Y \rightarrow W, d_Y : W \rightarrow Y)$ as invertible D/S function pairs. Then we can build the D/S functions for both the product and the sum:

$$s_{X \times Y} : X \times Y \rightarrow W, d_{X \times Y} : W \rightarrow X \times Y, s_{X + Y} : X + Y \rightarrow W, d_{X + Y} : W \rightarrow X + Y$$

Functionially, all these S/D functions $(s_X, s_Y) \mapsto s_{X \times Y}$, $(d_X, d_Y) \mapsto d_{X \times Y}$, $(s_X, s_Y) \mapsto s_{X + Y}$, $(d_X, d_Y) \mapsto d_{X + Y}$ can be generated automatically without human coding.

Generic types In **generic programming**[6], one can operate data types algebraically, i.e., build types from the other types as parameters, thus reducing duplicate code significantly, especially in functional programming. The simplest example is the array functor we mentioned previously:

```
// F send a type to the array of the type
// F: 'T -> 'T[]
// 'T is a generic type
F item = [| item |]
x':int[] = F x = [| x |]
```

Suppose we have the S/D functions $s : T \rightarrow W$ and $d : W \rightarrow T$, implementation of S/D function $F s : T[] \rightarrow W$ and $F d : W \rightarrow T[]$ is not difficult.

Just keep in mind that we need a functional programming idea that s and d are parameters as inputs. As shown in the following program, the S/D functions $F s$ and $F d$ are independent on type T :

```

// s: int -> byte[], serialization
let s (x:int) = x.ToBytes()

// d: byte[] * int -> int, deserialization
let d (bin:byte[],index:int) = Int.FromBinary(bin,index)

// Fs: (T -> byte[]) -> 'T[] -> byte[], serialization
let Fs (s:'T -> byte[]) (items: 'T[]) =
    let buffer = new List<byte[]>()
    items.Length.ToBytes() |> buffer.Add
    items
    |> Array.iter(fun item ->
        item |> s |> buffer.Add)
    buffer.bytes()

// Fd: (byte[] * int -> T) -> byte[] -> 'T[], deserialization
let Fd (d: byte[] * int -> 'T) (bin: byte[]) =
    let index = 0
    let length = Int.FromBinary(bin,index)
    index <- index + 4

    [| 0 .. length - 1 |]
    |> Array.map(fun i ->
        d(bin,index))

```

The similarly, the S/D functions of other generic types can be handled in a same way without considering the specific parameter types.

7 Conclusion and future works

This paper describes the RPC design approach in the form of a functor. The RPC design can be streamlined into the following steps:

- Expose a real function f (mostly on server-side) for remote call
- Apply RPC functor F for type mapping
- Generate the corresponding virtual local function $f' = Ff$

By implementing type sharing with automated serialization/deserialization coding, it is possible to make the functor work without much human coding. According to our experience of practice in commercial development projects, the functorial method significantly reduced the human labor in system

architecture design, debugging, testing, and documentation.

Furthermore, type sharing provides some transparency to allow us overcome the difficulty of cross-platform design. Thanks to the automated S/D coding, we can let as many as possible custom types shared among platforms, without the heavy burden of programming. Free manipulation of types among platforms can make the front end as complicated as the back end, and enhance the user experience to a high level.

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